

Deliverable 4.2

Cross-regional Exchange of Best Practices and Lessons Learnt

CTA
August 2025

R **BIN**

**DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH**

Funded by
the European Union

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON-CSA
PROJECT NUMBER	101060504
START DAY	1 September 2022
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	Cross-regional Exchange of Best Practices and Lessons Learnt
WORK PACKAGE	WP4
TASK	Task 4.2
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DATE	August 2025

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public, fully open	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Changes	Responsible partner
0.0	25/03/2025	Deliverable index	CTA
1.0	05/06/2025	Final draft version	CTA
2.0	28/08/2025	Final version	CTA

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACR+	Association of Cities and Regions for Sustainable Resource Management
AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
CAP/CAPADR	Consejería de Agricultura, Ganadería, Pesca y Desarrollo Rural
CBGMC	Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CTA	Fundación Corporación Tecnológica de Andalucía
EU	European Union
IFA/IFAPA	Andalusian Institute for Research and Training in Agriculture, Fisheries, Foods and Organic Production
LIST	Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology
MARC	Multi-Actor Regional Constellations
MLW	Mutual Learning Workshop
MoC	Memorandum of Collaboration
MTU	Munster Technological University
PED	PEDAL Consulting SRO
QPL	Q-Plan International Advisors PC
R&D	Research and Development
RCM	Region of Central Macedonia
S2i	Steinbeis 2I GMBH
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SRA	Southern Regional Assembly
WR	White Research SRL
ZSK	Rozvojova Agentura Zilinskeho Samospravného Kraja NO

1. Executive Summary

The ROBIN project's Task 4.2 has successfully demonstrated the power and necessity of cross-regional collaboration in advancing the circular bioeconomy across Europe. Through a comprehensive set of activities—including Mutual Learning Workshops, regional events, a Train-the-Trainer session, and the signing of a Memorandum of Collaboration—ROBIN has fostered a dynamic environment for knowledge exchange, capacity building, and policy innovation.

A central theme across all initiatives was the **promotion of mutual learning** and the **exchange of practical experiences** among regions. The two Mutual Learning Workshops (MLWs) served as pivotal moments for stakeholders from diverse backgrounds to share tools, methodologies, and policy insights. The 2nd MLW (especially Mentimeter results) provided important data for deliverable 4.3, mainly Policy Recommendations. These workshops not only facilitated the dissemination of the ROBIN Toolbox but also enabled participants to explore synergies with other EU-funded projects such as BIOMODEL4REGIONS, BIOTRANSFORM, CEE2ACT, ShapingBIO, SUSTRACK, or initiatives like the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI). The workshops emphasized governance models, stakeholder engagement, and sustainability assessment—core pillars of effective circular bioeconomy strategies.

The regional events held in Andalusia, Baden-Württemberg, Central Macedonia, the Southern Region of Ireland, and Žilina further reinforced the importance of localized engagement. Despite their geographical and cultural differences, these events shared several common goals:

- Strengthening regional governance through public-private partnerships and stakeholder networks.
- Testing and validating tools such as the ROBIN Toolbox.
- Promoting awareness and capacity building among regional actors.
- Encouraging interregional dialogue to identify shared challenges and co-develop solutions.

Each region tailored its event to its specific context while aligning with ROBIN's broader objectives, showcasing the adaptability and scalability of the project's methodologies.

The Train-the-Trainer event in Brussels exemplified ROBIN's commitment to scaling impact beyond the project's lifespan. By equipping regional representatives with the knowledge and pedagogical tools to train others, the project ensured that its methodologies could be replicated and adapted across Europe. The event also served as a platform for presenting the five-step Replication guidelines, which will be further detailed in the upcoming deliverable D4.3.

The Memorandum of Collaboration (MoC) signed by the five ROBIN regions marks a significant milestone in institutionalizing the project's legacy. The MoC outlines a shared vision for continued cooperation in areas such as governance innovation, policy alignment, and stakeholder engagement. It reflects a collective commitment to sustaining the momentum generated by ROBIN and to fostering a resilient, inclusive, and sustainable bioeconomy.

ROBIN's cross-regional exchange activities have proven that collaboration, adaptability, and shared learning are essential for accelerating the transition to a circular bioeconomy. The initiatives under Task 4.2 not only enhanced regional capacities but also laid the groundwork for a pan-European network of bioeconomy innovators. By aligning local actions with European strategies and fostering a culture of openness and cooperation, ROBIN has set a benchmark for future projects aiming to bridge policy, practice, and innovation in the bioeconomy sector.

2. Introduction

Objective of Work Package 4

WP4 focused on:

- 1) Monitored and assessed the project's outcomes, impacts and perceptions change (objective of task 4.1).
- 2) Exchanged best practices and lessons learned among the ROBIN targeted regions, and external ones (objective of task 4.1) and
- 3) Developed the ROBIN replication guideline and policy recommendations (objective of task 4.3).

2.1 Objective of task 4.2

This deliverable explains the work carried out and the main results obtained from ROBIN task 4.2.

The main axis of the activities performed under T4.2. is the exchange of knowledge and experiences gained from the ROBIN project development and implementation among the ROBIN regions, but also with external ones interested in regional bioeconomy policy implementation, during the project duration but also beyond it, to promote the development of cross-regional partnerships on regional bioeconomy, build partnerships and enhance openness, transparency and engagement.

To this end, the following actions were planned:

- 1) **Two Mutual Learning Workshops (MLW)** focused on relevant topics for the ROBIN project.
- 2) **Five regional events**, to support actions at national level by inviting other regions from the same country to participate.
- 3) **One Train-the-Trainer event**, aiming at building the capacity of an ever-increasing number of European regions beyond ROBIN ones, supporting a broader transition towards bio-based circular economies.
- 4) **One Memorandum of Collaboration (MoC)** through which the five ROBIN regions state their interest in regional bioeconomy and their intention to continue exchanging information about areas addressed by ROBIN after the project end.

2.2 Synergies between T4.2. and other ROBIN work packages and tasks

2.2.1 Synergies between task 4.2. and work package 3

Activities under WP3, especially those linked to T3.2. and T3.3., have the following direct links with what has been developed under T4.2.:

- 1) The first ROBIN Mutual Learning Workshop held in Stuttgart on 9 October 2024 focused on exchanging best practices with other EU projects and regional bioeconomy experts regarding the development of tools aiming at supporting regions in their transition to circular bioeconomy. This exchange of experiences and best practices contributed to the validation and improvement of the ROBIN toolbox.

- 2) The 2nd stakeholder engagement events in each ROBIN region, planned under the T3.2. beta-testing phase have been coordinated with the ROBIN regional events since both initiatives shared many of the same requirements and needs to be addressed and coincided in time.
- 3) The final version of the ROBIN toolbox developed under T3.3. has been used as the main content for the train-the-trainer event.

2.2.2 Synergies between task 4.2. and task 4.3

The following activities performed under task 4.2. have been designed and implemented in coordination and for the purpose of feeding ROBIN's practical Replication guidelines and Policy recommendations task (T4.3.):

- 1) The second ROBIN Mutual Learning Workshop (MLW) held online on 19 February 2025 focused on exchanging findings and presenting results linked to policy recommendations in circular bioeconomy. It included thematic hands-on sessions to work, together with the audience, on four specific hot topics, to gather relevant information for the project results. The Mentimeter tool was used during the 2nd MLW to gather real-time feedback and prioritise policy recommendations.
- 2) The train-the-trainer event was conceived, designed and implemented as a session for presenting the main elements of the replication guidelines for the ROBIN's methodology, becoming an opportunity to get first-hand information on what can be included or modified to make it more useful for target audiences.

3. The Importance and Benefits of Knowledge Exchange for the Development of the Circular Bioeconomy in Europe

For Europe to achieve social well-being, economic prosperity, and environmental sustainability, a strong circular bioeconomy must be established. The sharing of best practices, knowledge, and experiences among regions, projects, and pertinent stakeholders is one of the main forces behind this progress.

By enabling stakeholders to gain insight from one another's achievements and difficulties, knowledge exchange promotes innovation. By exchanging experiences, regions and projects can find successful strategies and steer clear of typical mistakes. This cooperative strategy speeds up the adoption of cutting-edge methods and technologies, resulting in bioeconomic processes that are more sustainable and effective. Furthermore, cooperation between various stakeholders—such as academics, policymakers, private sector, and consumers—promotes a multidisciplinary viewpoint that is critical for dealing with intricate bioeconomic issues.

Active knowledge-sharing puts regions in a better position to take advantage of their special assets and capabilities. They can improve their competitiveness in the bioeconomy sector by adapting best practices to their unique settings through learning from the experiences of other places. Furthermore, areas in the forefront of the circular bioeconomy can function as models for others, encouraging them to follow suit and help create a more sustainable Europe.

Building the capacity and skills of stakeholders in the circular bioeconomy is largely dependent on the sharing of best practices and knowledge. Conferences, workshops, and training sessions give participants the chance to network with peers, learn new skills, and keep current on industry advancements.

In conclusion, the growth of the circular bioeconomy in Europe depends on the sharing of best practices, knowledge, and experiences among regions, initiatives, and pertinent stakeholders. Innovation, regional competitiveness, capacity building, policy coherence, and community participation are all strengthened by it. Europe can hasten its shift to a robust and sustainable bioeconomy by adopting a cooperative strategy. By embracing a collaborative approach, Europe can accelerate its transition to a sustainable and resilient bioeconomy, benefiting both the environment and society.

For all the abovementioned reasons, the ROBIN project has implemented a broad number of multi-actor knowledge exchange activities at different governance levels, following a cross regional approach, offering mutual learning workshops, good practice exchange, training and long-lasting cooperation schemes, enabling stakeholders to learn from experiences in other regions, gain a deeper understanding of ROBIN's measures' inner workings and impact, as well as setting the path to a fruitful collaboration among ROBIN's regions even after the project ends.

4. Main activities performed

4.1 Mutual Learning Workshops

Mutual Learning Workshops are collaborative events designed to facilitate the exchange of knowledge, experiences, and best practices among participants from diverse backgrounds and regions. These workshops aim to create a dynamic environment where stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, industry professionals, and community members, come together to share insights and learn from one another. The primary goal of Mutual Learning Workshops was to foster innovation and improve practices by leveraging the collective expertise of the participants. By engaging in open dialogue and interactive sessions, attendees were able to identify common challenges, explore innovative solutions, and build networks that support ongoing collaboration. This approach not only enhances individual and organizational capabilities but also contributes to the development of more effective and sustainable strategies in various fields, including the circular bioeconomy.

Two Mutual Learning Workshops were led by ROBIN in collaboration with other projects and linked initiatives, focused on topics relevant for the ROBIN project and aligned with the project implementation plan, to maximize the impact of the exchange of information within the ROBIN results:

- Tools supporting the development of circular bioeconomy regional governance models, 1st ROBIN Mutual Learning Workshop, held in Stuttgart on 9 October 2024.
- Regional policy advocacy aimed at promoting the circular bioeconomy in Europe, 2nd ROBIN Mutual Learning Workshop, held online on 19 February 2025. The event, initially designed as a face-to-face event, was held online for several reasons:
 - The consortium meeting associated with this event was held online.
 - To facilitate the organization of the event and maximize the number of attendees.

4.1.1 1st ROBIN Mutual Learning Workshop

On 9 October 2024, **42 participants** attended (both online and onsite) the **First Mutual Learning Workshop** organised by S2i and held in Stuttgart.

The objective of this Mutual Learning Workshop was to share and exchange information about the work developed by several EU funded projects, **aimed at generating tools to support the creation and/or consolidation of regional governance mechanisms for the circular bioeconomy**, allowing participants to:

- Learn from these projects' experiences.
- Assess possible synergies among the different tools developed.
- Collaborate in the creation of mechanisms that promote the consolidation of the sector at the European level.

During the workshop, the ROBIN toolbox was presented to European regional authorities and other stakeholders interested in finding out which tools they can use to support circular bioeconomy governance, from both technical and regional perspectives.

The experience of tools development from the following initiatives was also shared, leading the audience to an open discussion about this topic, and exploring the **replication potential** of these projects' assets among European regions:

- Igor Kos, a representative from e-ZAVOD, shared valuable insights into developing a Circular Bioeconomy Strategy using the *Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)*¹ methodology, drawing from experiences in the Podravje-Maribor region of Slovenia.
- Jurijs Grizans, Senior Expert at ICLEI Europe and representative of BIOMODEL4REGIONS² discussed their tools that are designed to support regional bioeconomy governance, including governance analysis, monitoring, and development planning tools.
- Dr. Gitanjali Thakur from the Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology and representative of ROBIN's sister project BIOTRANSFORM³ presented how the sustainability assessment tool can contribute to optimising regional bioeconomy pathways.
- María Rosell from GEONARDO, representing CEE2ACT⁴, focused on empowering Central and Eastern European countries to formulate circular bioeconomy strategies.
- Lastly, Jana Bielikova from PEDAL Consulting introduced the SUSTRACK⁵ Monitoring Tool. The tool aims to help users access indicators, data, and methods that enhance their understanding of effective management for transitioning to a Circular Biobased Economy while linking indicators with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
- Patrick Bechhaus presented an overview of the upcoming CCRI Self-Assessment Tool and its functionality. It is interesting to see how the CCRI develops practical solutions for the selection of suitable indicators, the definition of targets and regular monitoring for the implementation of circular systemic approaches.

The main conclusions reached are described below:

- Collaboration between projects and initiatives to promote the bioeconomy as a strategic pillar for European regions and local administrations is of utmost importance
- It is necessary to develop regional performance measurement systems using available information and specific strategic KPIs.
- There is an urgency to coordinate tools into clear frameworks for territorial decision-makers to help them identify roadmaps based on their specific situations and immediate needs.
- Developing tools that are simple to use yet customizable to each region's geopolitical conditions and current governance models in the circular bioeconomy is critical.

1 <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/>

2 <https://www.biomodel4regions.eu/>

3 <https://www.biotransform-project.eu/>

4 <https://www.cee2act.eu/>

5 <https://sustrack.eu/>

AGENDA – 1st Mutual Learning Workshop

Date: 09/10/2024 | Start time: 09.30 CET

Venue: Steinbeis Europa Zentrum – [Leuschnerstr. 43](#), D-70176 Stuttgart, Germany – 5th floor

Registration link [here](#)

Contact persons:

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Time	Topic	Speakers
09:30 – 10:00	Attendants registration	-
10:00 – 10:05	Welcome session	María García (CTA)
10:05 – 10:25	"Development of a Circular Bioeconomy Strategy under the CCRI methodology prospective" – The experience of the Podravje-Maribor region	Igor Kos (E Zavod)
10:25 – 10:45	Presentation of ROBIN project	Margarita Angelidou (Q-PLAN)
10:45 – 11:00	Q&A session	-
11:00 – 12:15	Presentation of ROBIN toolbox <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From a technical point of view • From a regional point of view 	Nadja Schlichenmaier (S2i) Mar Cátedra (CAP) Anthoula Papadopoulou (RCM) Colm Walsh (SRA) Katarína Janurová (ZIL)
12:15 – 12:30	Q&A session	-
12:30 – 13:15	Lunch & learning	
13:15 – 13:30	Next ROBIN steps: external validation phase and open call	Christos Politis (Q-PLAN)
13:30 – 13:45	Q&A session	-
13:45 – 14:45	Invited projects' tools presentations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIOMODELS4REGIONS • BIOTRANSFORM • CEE2ACT • SUSTRACK • THE CCRI SELF-ASSESSMENT TOOL 	Jurijs Grizans (ICLEI) Gitanjali Thakur (LIST) María Beatriz Rosell (Geonardo) Jana Bielikova (PEDAL) Patrick Bechhaus (CCRI)
14:45 – 15:30	Open debate "Potential complementarities and synergies among tools, considering regions' needs"	Chaired by María García (CTA)
15:30	End of the workshop	

Figure 1. First Mutual Learning Workshop - Agenda

Figure 2. First Mutual Learning Workshop - Participants

4.1.2 2nd ROBIN Mutual Learning Workshop

The online event “BioFUTURE – Knowledge sharing for unlocking the potential of bioeconomy in Europe from the regional policy perspective”, with over 85 attendees from the quadruple helix, was organized in collaboration with the BIOMODEL4REGIONS, BIOTRANSFORM and ShapingBio projects.

Aimed at sharing the results of these projects related to regional policy advocacy for promoting the bioeconomy, the event focused on key themes identified during the projects’ implementation. Several pre-workshop meetings were held to select four of them, each presented by a representative of each of the projects participating in the event, providing practical insights and solutions for advancing these themes:

- Governance and Policy Alignment.
- Social and Regional Challenges, along with Public Awareness.
- Cross-sector Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement.
- Environmental Impact and Resource Efficiency.

These topics were discussed following a presentation of two representatives from the European Commission:

- Sarianne Tikkanen (EC, DG Environment), who spoke about the EU policy landscape and the update of the Bioeconomy Strategy.
- Tomasz Calikowski (EC, DG Research), who spoke about Green Transition and Bioeconomy Governance: The Role of Bio-Based Sector R&D.

Participants could learn from the projects’ findings and discussed how to apply these ideas in their regions. Additionally, representatives for other European projects gained valuable information to help identifying, analysing, designing, and implementing regional policies and governance models in their own work.

The workshop led to several significant conclusions:

- Enhanced inter-project dialogue: The event successfully strengthened cooperation and knowledge exchange between four Horizon Europe projects.
- Identification of shared challenges and priorities: Joint exploration of key issues including Key Environmental Risks Associated with Bioeconomies and their Ecological Impacts; and how social and regional factors influence the development of bioeconomy across the EU regions.
- Co-creation of a Top 10 Policy Topics list: Through cross-project discussions and pre-workshop consultations, the most pressing topics for advancing the bioeconomy were identified.
- Interactive methods for knowledge co-production: Use of online tools to facilitate participant input, resulting in actionable insights and shared recommendations.
- Contribution to strategic project outcomes: Insights from the workshop directly informed project deliverables (notably D4.3 in the case of ROBIN).

D4.2.: Cross-regional Exchange of Best Practices and Lessons Learnt. August 2025

Times	Topics	Speakers
09:30—09:35	Introduction and welcome session	María-García (CTA)
09:35—09:50	Keynote Speech—“EU policy landscape and the update of the Bioeconomy Strategy”	Sariänne-Tikkanen (EC, DG-Environment)
09:50—10:00	Keynote Speech—“Bioeconomy governance: the case of bio-based sector R&D (while not leaving anyone behind)”	Tomasz-Calkowski (EC, DG-Research)
10:00—10:15	Our projects in a nutshell: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → BIOMODEL4REGIONS → BIOTRANSFORM → ROBIN → SHAPINGBIO 	Karolina-Jurkiewicz (APRE) Anita-Lombardo (ACR+) Christos-Politis (Q-PLAN) Francesca-Santaniello/Flavia-Marucci (APRE)
10:15—10:30	Our policy trending topics (top 10 list)	Adriana-Ciefova (PEDAL)
10:30—11:30	Thematic sessions (1 st part): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Governance and Policy Alignment → Social and Regional Policy Challenges and Public Awareness 	Anita-Lombardo (ACR+) Adriana-Ciefova (PEDAL)
11:30—11:40	Break	
11:40—12:40	Thematic sessions (2 nd part): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Cross-Sectoral Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement → Environmental Impact and Resource Efficiency 	Jurij-Grizans (CLEI) Francesca-Santaniello (APRE)
12:40—12:45	Wrap-up and farewells	María-García (CTA)
12:45	End-of-the-workshop	

Figure 3. Second Mutual Learning Workshop - Agenda

The figure consists of four screenshots from the workshop:

- Top Left:** Title slide for the 19-02-25 BioFUTURE Mutual Learning Workshop, focusing on knowledge sharing for unlocking the potential of bioeconomy in Europe from the regional policy perspective. Logos for ROBIN, BIOMODEL4REGIONS, ShapingBio, and BIOTRANSFORM are visible.
- Top Right:** A slide titled "Why EU needs to act: key data on biomass supply and use". It features a donut chart showing biomass supply and demand. Key points include: supply mostly covered by agriculture and forestry; demand is divided (40% for animal feed and bedding, ~30% for material use, >20% for bioenergy); and potential to boost circularity and recycling by valorizing bio-waste and by-products.
- Bottom Left:** A slide titled "Collaboration is an essential element" with a 2x3 grid of boxes: "Complexity of the bio-based economy sectors", "Innovative solutions through knowledge sharing", "Holistic and innovative approach", "Policy and regulatory alignment", "Market development and value chains", "Resource efficiency and circular economy", "Risk management and problem solving", and "Building trust and creating networks".
- Bottom Right:** A poll question: "What governance and policy actions should be prioritized to support the circular bioeconomy and related social and regional challenges?". The poll results show 6 options, with the 1st option (regulatory framework) being the most selected.

Figure 4. Second Mutual Learning Workshop - Screenshots

4.2 Regional events

The regional events were conceived as opportunities for regional partners to organise physical and virtual events to support actions at the national level by inviting other regions from the same country to participate, aiming at developing partnerships on regional bioeconomy, exchange knowledge and experience, enhance openness, transparency and engagement towards the ROBIN project and its main activities.

Observing the alignment of these events in terms of objective and timeline with the regional beta testing events planned within task 3.2., both initiatives were designed and developed in coordination (more information available in ROBIN's deliverable 3.2. "Report on ROBIN Toolbox Validation and Update").⁶

As a result, the following regional events were performed:

4.2.1 Regional event: Andalusia

Responsible entities: CAP, IFA and CTA.

Date: 13/03/2025

Participants: 28 attendees, including project partners, Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARC) members and representatives from three external regions.

This regional event was carried out in Malaga on 13 March 2025 in the framework of a national reference event on knowledge transfer and innovation (TRANSFIERE Forum).

The aim of this workshop was to exchange ideas about a potential public-private partnership structure in Andalusia, building on existing public-private cooperation structure and synergies in different participating Spanish regions.

Three external regions from Spain were invited to present their experience and exchange on the topic:

- Catalonia.
- Madrid.
- Castilla and León.

To further explore the design and future implementation of a public-private partnership framework, participants from external regions, regional stakeholders and Andalusian MARC members used the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas (CBGMC) tool to incorporate their insights, focusing on key aspects such as activities, partnerships, resources, regional vision and communication channels.

The event concluded with the identification of further potential synergies between the regions in the future.

¹ https://robin-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/D3.2_final-version.pdf

AGENDA

Evento regional: Intercambio de experiencias en bioeconomía circular en el marco del proyecto ROBIN

13 de marzo de 2025

Foro Transfiere 2025 - Málaga

12:00 - 12:15 | Introducción y presentación del proyecto ROBIN

- **Bienvenida** a los asistentes y presentación de objetivos. Mar Cátedra (CAPADR), Samir Sayadi (IFAPA) y María García (CTA).
- **Descripción del proyecto ROBIN**, con especial énfasis en la "Toolbox" de herramientas desarrolladas. María García (CTA).

12:15 - 13:30 | Sesión 1: Caso práctico - Colaboración público-privada en bioeconomía

Coordina la sesión Samir Sayadi (IFAPA).

- **Intercambio de experiencias:** Presentación y debate sobre las estructuras de colaboración público-privada desarrolladas por las regiones participantes.
 - Cataluña. Víctor Falguera. Hub de la Bioeconomía de Cataluña (BioHubCat).
 - Madrid. José Luis Cruz. Instituto Madrileño de Investigación y Desarrollo Rural, Agrario y Alimentario (IMIDRA).
 - Castilla y León. Jesús Ángel Díez Vázquez. Fundación Patrimonio Natural de Castilla y León.
 - Andalucía. Mar Cátedra Cerón. Secretaría General de Agricultura, Ganadería y Alimentación. Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural de la Junta de Andalucía.
- **Ejercicio práctico:** Aplicación de la herramienta canvas de la "Toolbox" del proyecto ROBIN para diseñar una potencial estructura de colaboración público-privada.
- **Debate:** Identificación de sinergias entre las regiones para fortalecer la colaboración.

13:30 - 14:00 | Sesión 2: Potencial del canvas para la colaboración público-privada

Coordina la sesión Samir Sayadi (IFAPA).

- **Feedback** de todos los asistentes.
- **Propuestas de mejora** y exploración de nuevas sinergias.

14:00 - 15:00 | Cóctel - Networking

- Espacio para **networking** y discusión informal sobre posibles colaboraciones futuras entre las personas participantes.

Figure 5. Andalusia Regional Event - Agenda

Figure 6. Andalusia Regional Event - Attendees

4.2.2 Regional event: Baden-Württemberg

Responsible entities: S2I.

Date: 06/02/2025

Participants: 16 stakeholders from academia, public administration/policy and civil society.

S2I developed a regional workshop aiming at fostering the exchange of information, experience and knowledge between stakeholders from different regions of Germany (and Slovenia), combining a theoretical part (tools and methods) as well as an applied part (sharing concrete experience of regions that used the presented tools and methods), structured in three sessions:

- Session 1: Exchange on existing **tools and methods focused on developing, implementing and monitoring bioeconomy strategies** (including ROBIN toolbox & Policy Monitoring System): the first session concentrated (based on presentation of tools and methodologies to do so).
- Session 2: Exchange of experience on the preparation process of **bioeconomy strategies in urban & rural areas**.
- Session 3: Exchange on **monitoring the implementation of bioeconomy strategies**.

The action directly contributed to support representatives from 3 external regions, Hessen and North-Rhine-Westphalia in Germany and Podravje in Slovenia, to exchange information, share experiences and learn from each other. It helped strengthen ties between the stakeholders and support a coalition dedicated to promoting bioeconomy in Baden-Württemberg, in Germany and in Europe.

AGENDA

Zeit	Thema	Referent
10.00 – 10.30	Begrüßung, Ziele des Workshops und Vorstellungsrunde	Dr. Clémentine Roth – S2i
Session I: Austausch über Tools und Methodik		
10.30 – 10.55	ROBIN-Projekt und Tools	Dr. Clémentine Roth – S2i
10.55 – 11.20	CCRI self-assessment tool	Jannis Lambert – PROGNOSE AG / CCRI
11.20 – 11.45	Urban BioÖkonomieLab-Methodik	Dr.-Ing. Marius Mohr – Fraunhofer IGB
11.45 – 12.30	Mittagessen & Networking	
Session II: Austausch über Entwicklung von Bioökonomie Strategien in urbanen und ländlichen Räumen		
12.30 – 13.30	Urbane/industrielle Räume	Lenz Sulzer – Technologie Region Karlsruhe Igor Kos – eZavod / Podravje Region Dr. Christian Klar – BioökonomieREVIER
	Ländliche Räume	Simon Kaufhold (Alb-Donau-Kreis)
Session III: Austausch über Monitoring von Implementierung		
14.00 – 14.50	Moderierte Austauschrunde	
14.50 – 15.00	Feedback, Schlussfolgerung und nächste Schritte	Dr. Clémentine Roth – S2i
15.00	Ende der Veranstaltung	

Figure 7. Baden-Württemberg Regional Event - Agenda

Figure 8. Baden-Württemberg Regional Event - Attendees

4.2.3 Regional event: Central Macedonia

Responsible entities: RCM, AUTH and QPL.

Date: 27/02/2025

Participants: 53 attendees, including project partners, regional stakeholders and representatives from four external regions.

On 27 February 2025, the regional workshop took place in Thessaloniki, organized by the Region of Central Macedonia through its Department of European Programmes and Synergies and the Department of Industry, Energy and Natural Resources with contribution from Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH).

The primary objectives of the workshop were:

- To introduce stakeholders to the ROBIN Toolbox and its functionalities.
- To collect feedback from regional and interregional stakeholders regarding its usability and applicability.
- **To exchange knowledge on Circular Bioeconomy initiatives and best practices.**
- **To discuss the potential establishment of a Regional Bioeconomy Cluster**, aiming to bring together key actors from various sectors to collaborate on sustainable initiatives.
- To foster networking among organizations engaged in sustainable bioeconomic strategies.

The workshop included participation from 4 regions beyond the Region of Central Macedonia, including:

- Region of Central Greece
- Region of Thessaly
- Region of Western Macedonia
- Region of Western Greece

**Laboratory for the Evaluation of Circular Bioeconomy Tools
Beta Testing Workshop**

Thursday 27 February 2025

Meeting room of the Regional Council of Central Macedonia
(64 26th October Street, [Thessaloniki](#))

TIME	THEMATIC	SPEAKERS
09.30 - 10.00	Attendance – Registration	
10.00 - 10.15	Welcome and Introduction	Region of Central Macedonia
10.15 - 10.35	The Circular Economy in the Region of Central Macedonia	Region of Central Macedonia Dimitris Vlachos Anthoula Papadopoulou
10.35 - 11.30	Tools of the European project ROBIN for the promotion of the Circular Economy in the Region of Central Macedonia Presentation of the ROBIN Toolkit & Questionnaire Research	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki Alexandros Skondras Iphigenia Skalidi
11.30 - 12.00	Coffee break	
12.00 - 12.40	Workshop on Tool Evaluation and Application in the Regions	Region of Central Macedonia
12.40 - 13.00	Presentation of Good Practices in the Region of Central Macedonia	Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia Chrysanthi Kiskini Kyriaki Kissa
13.00 - 14.00	Creation of a Regional Bioeconomy Cluster	QPLAN Christos Politis Andromachi Boykou
14.00 - 15.30	Networking Lunch	
15.30 - 16.00	Conclusions-Next Actions ROBIN's next steps, future actions of the MSM in the field of the bioeconomy and a satisfaction survey	Region of Central Macedonia

Figure 9. Region of Central Macedonia Event - Agenda

Figure 10. Region of Central Macedonia Event - Attendees

4.2.4 Regional event: Southern Region

Responsible entities: SRA and MTU.

Date: 15/10/2024

Participants: 28 attendees, including project partners, MARC members and representatives from the two other regional authorities that together with Southern Regional Assembly comprise the regional tier of government in Ireland (Northern & Western Regional Assembly and Eastern & Midland Regional Assembly).

The event was held during the Bioeconomy Ireland Week 2024 in Assembly House in Waterford, Ireland, and brought together a panel of expert speakers who delivered presentations on different aspects of bioeconomy from finance to governance.

There followed a questions and answer session and discussion that set the scene for a deeper exploration of our themes during our ROBIN Tools validation workshop.

The second part of our event focussed on the ROBIN Project. Attendees were given an overview of the Project and an update of Project activities carried out to date by the Irish partners.

The main outcomes of this action were twofold:

- 1) **To raise awareness of the bioeconomy in the region**, with a special focus on developing biomethane opportunities, **funding opportunities and bioeconomy governance**.
- 2) To successfully manage and deliver a beta validation workshop concerning two Toolbox resources – namely, the Canvas and the Policy Monitoring System.

The quality of the presentations and the ensuing discussion and ROBIN tool validation workshop were of immense benefit to those in attendance based on feedback received, and a great many new contacts were made through informal networking.

Figure 11. Southern Region Regional Event - Agenda

Figure 12. Southern Region Regional Event - Attendees

4.2.5 Regional event: Žilina

Responsible entities: ZSK and PED.

Date: 04/12/2024

Participants: 40 attendees, 36 stakeholders coming from the Žilina Region and from 4 Slovak external regions.

A workshop titled "Together for the Slovak Bioeconomy" was organized by PED in collaboration with ZSK. The event was held at the premises of the Žilina Self-Governing Region on 4 December 2024, where the main findings of the "Regional Analysis of the Development of Bioeconomy in the Žilina Region" were presented by the experts who conducted the analysis.

During the workshop, two external regions – Banská Bystrica region and Trenčín region – presented their current state of bioeconomy development, together with the examples of their most successful bioeconomy pilot projects, activities and plans.

An important part of the workshop was the Mutual Learning Session – open discussion linked to the **exchange of best practices and knowledge** among the participating regions (also the stakeholders from Prešov and Nitra regions participated at the event) which brought many interesting ideas for cooperation with the aim of **accelerating the transition of Slovak regions to the circular bioeconomy**.

The workshop included participation from 4 regions beyond the Žilina Region:

- Banská Bystrica Region (also the presenter)
- Trenčín Region (also the presenter)
- Prešov Region (the participant only)
- Nitra Region (the participant only)

The fact that the workshop was attended by the representatives of public authorities from other 4 Slovak regions brought many important insights and ideas to the Mutual Learning Session as well as to the informal talks among the participants.

Invitation to the ROBIN Workshop "Together for the Slovak bioeconomy"

Date: Wednesday 04.12.2024
Time: 10:00 – 13:00 CET
Place: Headquarters of the Žilina Self-governing Region
 Komenského 48, 011 09 Žilina

Circular bioeconomy represents an innovative way to efficiently use natural resources and biological waste, thereby supporting sustainable development, strengthening local economies, and at the same time reducing the burden on the environment. For the Slovak regions, the bioeconomy is the key to maintain jobs, increase competitiveness and build environmentally resilient communities.

The Regional Agency of the Žilina Self-Governing Region and PEDAL Consulting, s.r.o. in cooperation with the Žilina Self-Governing Region, would like to invite you to our next **ROBIN Workshop "Together for the Slovak Bioeconomy"**, which will take place on **Wednesday 4 December 4 2024** at 10:00 at the headquarters of the **Žilina Self-governing Region at Komenského 48 in Žilina**.

Our workshop is an opportunity to get familiar with the results of the ROBIN project in the Žilina Region, the aim of which is to support the regions in their transition to the circular bioeconomy. The project does so by creating and demonstrating the potential of innovative models and management structures of bioeconomy in selected 5 European regions: Andalusia (Spain), Baden-Württemberg (Germany), Southern Region (Ireland), Central Macedonia (Greece) and Žilina Region (Slovakia).

The event will also offer the presentation of the tools of the ROBIN Toolbox, as well as the summary of the current state of bioeconomy development not only in the Žilina Region, which is one of the ROBIN's pilot regions, but also in the other two invited regions in Slovakia. An important part of the workshop is the Mutual Learning Session, i.e. open discussion linked to the exchange of best practices and knowledge among the participating regions. Last but not least, the essential ambition of the workshop is informal networking and the searching for the opportunities for cooperation among the participating stakeholders with the aim of accelerating the transition of Slovak regions to the circular bioeconomy.

Draft Agenda:

09:45 – 10:00	Registration and Welcome Coffee
10:00 – 10:20	Welcome speech and Presentation of the current state of bioeconomy development in the Žilina Region
10:20 – 10:50	Presentation of the ROBIN project results in the Žilina region, and the ROBIN Toolbox tools
10:50 – 11:00	Presentation of the current state of bioeconomy development in the Banská Bystrica region
11:00 – 11:10	Presentation of the current state of bioeconomy development in the Trenčín/Prešov region
11:10 – 11:40	Networking Coffee Break
11:40 – 13:00	Mutual Learning Session: Discussion and exchange of best practices and knowledge among the regions
13:00 – 14:00	Joint Networking Lunch

PARTNERS

Figure 13. Žilina Regional Event - Agenda

Figure 14. Žilina Regional Event - Attendees

As a result of the ROBIN regional events, a total of 165 attendees from 21 regions (5 from the ROBIN project and 16 external) were involved, exchanging on relevant topics for boosting the circular bioeconomy in regions as

- Development of public-private partnership structures (such as nodes, hubs or clusters).
- Tools and methods to develop, implement and monitor bioeconomy strategies.
- Bioeconomy strategies in urban & rural areas.
- Knowledge exchange on Circular Bioeconomy initiatives and best practices.
- Promote awareness of the bioeconomy in the region.
- Funding opportunities.
- Bioeconomy governance.

4.3 Train-the-trainer event

As a general concept, the Train-the-trainer events are specialized programs designed to equip experienced individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively train others within an organization or community about a topic. These events focus not only on the subject matter being taught but also on the methodologies and strategies of education, communication, and facilitation. The ultimate goal is to create a ripple effect—by training a small group of trainers, initiatives can scale up their impact efforts efficiently and consistently across larger groups.

This approach is widely used where knowledge transfer and capacity building are essential for replication purposes. By empowering trainers with both content expertise and pedagogical skills, train-the-trainer events ensure that learning is sustainable, impactful, and aligned with organizational goals.

ROBIN's Train-the-Trainer Workshop, under the theme "Scaling the Bioeconomy Through ROBIN's Toolbox, Policies, and Strategies", was held in Brussels on the 14th of May 2025.

This interactive hybrid workshop brought together stakeholders from across Europe to delve into effective governance models, policy frameworks, and explore strategic tools aimed at fostering sustainable rural bioeconomy.

The main focus of the session was on the design, analysis, and implementation of governance models tailored for rural bioeconomy development. Participants engaged in interactive discussions and practical exercises exploring how ROBIN's Toolbox can be leveraged to enhance regional capacity, build resilience, and promote circular economic practices tailored to local needs.

During the event, the methodology performed and implemented within the project, structured in different "steps" following an overall guiding thread, was presented and explained in detail:

- First Replication Step: Building Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARC) and Stakeholder Engagement.
- Second Replication Step: Analyzing Governance Models and Policies.
- Third Replication Step: Designing and Deploying Governance Models.
- Fourth Replication Step: Using the ROBIN Toolbox.
- Fifth Replication Step: Monitoring and Evaluation.

This methodology is explained in detail in deliverable 4.3.

One of the workshop's key highlights was a panel of regional representatives, who shared firsthand experiences and lessons learned from piloting ROBIN's methodologies. These valuable insights and success stories were presented by stakeholders from:

- Andalusia (Spain)
- Baden-Württemberg (Germany)
- Central Macedonia (Greece)
- Southern Region (Ireland)
- Zilina (Slovakia)

Their contributions underscored the importance of strategies, cross-regional collaboration, and the value of a shared platform for knowledge exchange in scaling up circular bioeconomy initiatives.

At content level, as the event used the replication guidelines developed under task 4.3., more information of each of the ROBIN's methodology steps will be available from August 2025 in D4.3. "Replication Guide and Toolkit" in ROBIN's website⁷.

The event was performed as part of the European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference, a collaborative effort of six Horizon Europe projects: ROBIN⁸, MainstreamBIO⁹, SCALE-UP¹⁰, BioRural¹¹, BIOMODEL4REGIONS¹², and RuralBioUP¹³; all members of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance¹⁴.

The conference's goal was to promote and drive innovation, policy recommendations, and real-world applications of bioeconomy across Europe. Key stakeholders from local communities, policymaking, industry, and rural communities were the target audience, to discuss the approaches and strategies implemented by the projects.

After a coordinated dissemination and communication effort, targeting regional representatives (including Committee of Regions), other circular bioeconomy projects partners, project officers, and other stakeholders, a total of 32 people attended the event either onsite (24) or online (8).

7 <https://robin-project.eu/deliverables/>

8 <https://robin-project.eu/>

9 <https://mainstreambio-project.eu/>

10 <https://www.scaleup-bioeconomy.eu/es/inicio/>

11 <https://biorural.eu/>

12 <https://www.biomodel4regions.eu/>

13 <https://www.ruralbioup.eu/>

14 <https://robin-project.eu/robin-project-is-a-member-of-the-rural-bioeconomy-alliance/>

ROBIN Train-the-Trainer Workshop

Scaling the Bioeconomy through ROBIN's Toolbox, Policies, and Strategies

Date: 14/05/2025 | Start time: 11.15 CET

Venue: [Comet Louise](#), Room 3.4, Brussels

Online link: [here](#)

Registration form [here](#)

Contact persons:

- Content: María García (CTA) – maria.garcia@corporaciontecnologica.com
- Logistics: Ioanna Nydrioti (WR) - inydrioti@white-research.eu
Artemis Grigoriadou (WR) – agrigoriadou@white-research.eu

Time	Topic	Speakers
11.15-11.20 (5 min)	Introduction and welcome session	María García (CTA)
11.20-11.30 (10 min)	ROBIN project in a nutshell	Christos Politis (Q-PLAN)
11:30-11:45 (15 min)	ROBIN Replication Guide – General overview	Adriana Čiefová (PED)
11:45-11:55 (10 min)	First Replication Step: Building Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARC)s and Stakeholder Engagement	Ioanna Nydrioti (WR)
11:55-12:05 (10 min)	Second Replication Step: Analyzing Governance Models and Policies	Ifigeneia Skalidi (AUTH)
12:05-12:15 (10 min)	Third Replication Step: Designing and Deploying Governance Models	María García (CTA)
12:15-12:50 (35 min - app. 7 min each region)	Regional nodes experience: Andalusia (ES) Baden-Württemberg (DE) Central Macedonia (EL) Southern Region (IE) Zilina (SK)	María García (CTA) Clémentine Roth (S2I) Anthoula Papadopoulou (RCM) Colm Walsh (SRA) Katarína Janurová (ZSK)
12:50-13:05 (15 min)	Fourth Replication Step: Using the ROBIN Toolbox	Clémentine Roth (S2I)
13:05-13:15 (10 min)	Fifth Replication Step: Monitoring and Evaluation	Adriana Čiefová (PED)
13:15-13.30	Q&A Session	ALL
13.30	End of the workshop	

Figure 16. Train-the-trainer - Pictures

4.4 Memorandum of Collaboration

On the 13th of May 2025, in the framework of the ROBIN's final event within the European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference, the Region of Andalusia (represented by the "Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua, y Desarrollo Rural"), the Region of Baden-Württemberg (represented by the "Europabeauftragte der Ministerin für Wirtschaft, Arbeit und Tourismus des Landes Baden-Württemberg"), the Region of Central Macedonia (represented by the "General Directorate of Development and Environment), the Southern Region of Ireland (represented by the Southern Regional Assembly) and the Region of Zilina (represented by the "Rozvojová agentúra Žilinského samosprávneho kraja") signed a Memorandum of Collaboration (hereinafter MoC) to formally express their interest in developing regional bioeconomy and their intention to continue exchanging information about the different areas addressed by the ROBIN project after its conclusion.

Specifically, the MoC aims to deepen the cooperation between the ROBIN regions towards the achievement of the following objectives:

- Raise awareness among policy-makers and other interested parties towards (i) the circular bioeconomy concept and its relevance, (ii) opportunities in the exploitation of regional bioeconomy resources, (iii) new governance models and structures; (iv) strengthening bioeconomy regional innovation ecosystems; (v) new tools that, if widely adopted, can positively contribute to deploying circular bioeconomies; and (vi) anything else that could contribute increasing citizens' and consumers' awareness about bioeconomy.
- Improve the overall quality of regional policymaking, disseminating tools and methods such as the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas, the Bioeconomy Policy Monitoring Tool or the Environmental Protection Planning Tool (as they were developed and used in ROBIN).
- Support enhanced exchanges between the regions on policy insights and funding opportunities and facilitate the sharing of good practices between them.
- Create synergies by organizing common actions or events and making the best use of each region's strengths and capacities.
- Promote the exchange of innovative practices, research, and technologies among regions to accelerate the transition to a circular bioeconomy.
- Support local stakeholders in building capacity and knowledge to implement circular bioeconomy solutions tailored to regional needs and contexts.

Given the shared objectives, the regions agreed to strengthen their cooperation, including but not limited to the following areas:

- Circular bioeconomy.
- Bioeconomy innovation ecosystems.
- Multi-level regional governance.
- Good Governance Practices. Smart Specialization and Digitalization.
- Inclusive, resilient and sustainable regional development.
- Social innovation.

The full signed document is available in Annex I.

5. Conclusion

The ROBIN project, under Task 4.2, has successfully implemented a comprehensive and multi-level strategy to foster the exchange of best practices and lessons learnt among European regions. This task has been instrumental in promoting the development of circular bioeconomy governance models by facilitating collaboration, knowledge transfer, and capacity building across diverse regional contexts. The initiatives carried out under this task reflect a shared commitment to innovation, sustainability, and inclusive regional development.

A Strategic Framework for Knowledge Exchange

At the heart of Task 4.2 lies the recognition that the transition to a circular bioeconomy cannot be achieved in isolation. Instead, it requires a coordinated effort among regions, institutions, and stakeholders. The ROBIN project addressed this need by organizing a series of interlinked activities designed to maximize learning opportunities and foster long-term cooperation, including:

- **Two Mutual Learning Workshops (MLWs)** that brought together stakeholders from across Europe to share tools, methodologies, and policy insights.
- **Five regional events** tailored to the specific needs and contexts of the ROBIN partner regions, while maintaining a common structure and purpose.
- **A Train-the-Trainer event** aimed at scaling the project's impact by empowering regional actors to disseminate knowledge and practices.
- **A Memorandum of Collaboration (MoC)** signed by all five ROBIN regions, formalizing their commitment to continued cooperation beyond the project's duration.

These activities were not isolated efforts but were strategically aligned with other work packages and tasks within the ROBIN project, particularly WP3 and Task 4.3. This ensured coherence, avoided duplication, and enhanced the overall impact of the project.

Shared Themes and Common Objectives

Despite the diversity of the partner regions—ranging from Andalusia in Spain to Žilina in Slovakia—several common themes emerged across the initiatives:

1. **Governance and Policy Innovation:** All regions emphasized the importance of developing robust governance models tailored to their specific socio-economic and environmental contexts. The ROBIN Toolbox, including tools like the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas and the Policy Monitoring System, played a central role in these efforts.
2. **Stakeholder Engagement and Capacity Building:** The creation of Multi-Actor Regional Constellations and the organization of participatory events ensured that a wide range of voices—including public authorities, academia, industry, and civil society—were involved in shaping regional bioeconomy strategies.
3. **Replication and Scalability:** The Train-the-Trainer event and the Replication guidelines developed under Task 4.3 provided a clear roadmap for other regions to adopt and adapt ROBIN's methodologies. This approach ensures that the project's impact extends well beyond its original scope.

4. **Cross-Regional Learning and Synergies:** The regional events and MLWs facilitated the identification of synergies between regions, enabling them to learn from each other's successes and challenges. This collaborative spirit was further reinforced by the MoC, which outlines a framework for ongoing cooperation.
5. **Awareness and Advocacy:** Several events, such as the one held on 16 October 2023¹⁵ during Bioeconomy Ireland Week 2023, focused on raising awareness about the circular bioeconomy and advocating for supportive policies at the regional and national levels.

Impact and Legacy

The impact of Task 4.2 is evident in both tangible and intangible outcomes. Tangibly:

- **Over 320 participants from multiple regions engaged in the project's activities**, contributing to a rich exchange of ideas and practices. Intangibly, the project has fostered a culture of openness, collaboration, and innovation that will continue to influence regional bioeconomy strategies in the years to come.
- **Materialisation of activities in coordination with 9 projects and initiatives** from the clustering network built by the project along its implementation, **as well as 16 external regions** from ROBIN partners' countries.

The signing of the Memorandum of Collaboration is particularly noteworthy. It not only formalizes the commitment of the ROBIN regions to continue working together but also sets a precedent for other regions to follow. The MoC outlines shared goals such as improving policy quality, promoting innovation, and supporting local stakeholders—goals that are essential for building a resilient and inclusive circular bioeconomy.

In summary, Task 4.2 of the ROBIN project has demonstrated the transformative potential of cross-regional knowledge exchange in advancing the circular bioeconomy. By combining strategic planning, inclusive participation, and practical tools, the project has created a robust framework for regional cooperation and innovation. The shared experiences and lessons learnt through this task not only strengthen the participating regions but also contribute to a broader European vision of sustainability, resilience, and prosperity.

As Europe continues its transition towards a circular bioeconomy, the approaches and outcomes of the ROBIN project offer valuable insights and models for replication. The legacy of Task 4.2 lies not only in the tools and events it delivered but also in the enduring partnerships and collaborative spirit it has fostered.

¹⁵ <https://robin-project.eu/event/bioeconomy-ireland-week-2023/>

6. Annexes

6.1 Annex I. ROBIN's Memorandum of Collaboration

1. Introduction

The Region of Andalusia (Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua, y Desarrollo Rural), Region of Baden-Württemberg (Europabeauftragte der Ministerin für Wirtschaft, Arbeit und Tourismus des Landes Baden-Württemberg), Region of Central Macedonia (General Directorate of Development and Environment), Southern Region of Ireland (Southern Regional Assembly) and Region of Zilina (Rozvojova agentura Zilinskeho samospravného kraja), hereinafter referred to as the "Parties",

Whereas:

- *Noting* the shared values and objectives that guide their activities and underline their strategic planning. In particular, the Parties have interest in deploying circular bioeconomy at regional level, while promoting social innovation, as a way for boosting resilient and economic development for their territories.
- *Considering* that collaboration between Europe's Regional Authorities is critical, as it (i) allows policy-makers at the regional level to come together to share their experiences, plans and successes, (2) helps them shape more targeted, informed and effective policies; given that many challenges span multiple jurisdictions, (3) collaboration allows them to address problems they would not be able to solve independently and, furthermore, in an era of scarce resources, (4) regional leaders can benefit from the increased efficiencies of regional collaboration.
- *Having* regard to the fruitful cooperation that the Parties had in the most recent years. In the frame of the ROBIN project (Grant Agreement No 101060504), the Parties worked together on adapting their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets, while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts. They organized workshops, set agendas and roadmaps, discussed their performance and outcomes and exchanged valuable knowledge and past experiences.
- *Convinced* that closer cooperation between the Parties will serve their shared objectives, draw on their comparative strengths and offer added value to their respective activities, and wishing to look forward to further opportunities for their cooperation.

Agree as follows:

2. Objectives and Areas of Collaboration

Objectives

The present Memorandum of Collaboration (MoC) aims to deepen the cooperation between the Parties towards the achievement of the following objectives:

- to raise awareness among policy-makers and other interested parties towards (i) the circular bioeconomy concept and its relevance, (ii) opportunities in the exploitation of regional bioeconomy resources, (iii) new governance models and structures; (iv) strengthening bioeconomy regional innovation ecosystems; (v) new tools that, if widely adopted, can positively contribute to deploying circular bioeconomies; and (vi) anything else that could contribute to increase citizens' and consumers' awareness about bioeconomy.
- to improve the overall quality of regional policymaking, disseminating tools and methods such as the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas, the Bioeconomy Policy Monitoring Tool or the Environmental Protection Planning Tool (as they were developed and used in ROBIN).
- to support enhanced exchanges between the Parties on policy insights and funding opportunities and facilitate the sharing of good practices between them.

- to create synergies by organizing common actions or events and making the best use of each Party's strengths and capacities.
- to promote the exchange of innovative practices, research, and technologies among regions to accelerate the transition to a circular bioeconomy.
- to support local stakeholders in building capacity and knowledge to implement circular bioeconomy solutions tailored to regional needs and contexts.

Areas of Collaboration

- Given the shared objectives, the Parties agree to strengthen their cooperation, including but not limited to the following areas:
- Circular bioeconomy.
- Bioeconomy innovation ecosystems.
- Multi-level regional governance.
- Good Governance Practices, Smart Specialization and Digitalization.
- Inclusive, resilient and sustainable regional development.
- Social innovation.

3. Forms of Collaboration and Working method

Forms of Collaboration

The Parties agree to consider cooperation by various means, including but not limited to:

- joint events, seminars, workshops;
- joint awareness-raising campaigns;
- joint implementation of programs and/or projects;
- exchange of information and past experiences (e.g. current/future calls for funding in research/innovation projects);
- participation of experts in meetings;
- staff visits on a short-term basis for enhanced knowledge exchanges;

Supporters

The following ROBIN project partners have expressed their keen support to the Parties in making good use of the project tools and methodologies:

- Q-PLAN International Advisors PC (Q-PLAN): Christos Politis (politis@qplan-intl.gr)
- Fundación Corporación Tecnológica de Andalucía (CTA): María García Alegre (maria.garcia@corporaciontecnologica.com)
- White Research SRL (WR): Ioanna Nydrioti (inydrioti@white-research.eu)
- Pedal Consulting s.r.o.: Adriana Čiefová (a.ciefova@pedal-consulting.eu)
- Steinbeis 2i GmbH (SEZ): Clémentine Roth (clementine.roth@steinbeis-europa.de)
- Munster Technological University (MTU): Dragica Grozdanic (dragica.grozdanic@mtu.ie) and James Gaffey (james.gaffey@mtu.ie)
- Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (AUTH): Efstratios Stylianidis (ssstyl@auth.gr)
- Instituto Andaluz de Investigación y Formación Agraria, Pesquera, Alimentaria y de la Producción Ecológica (IFA): Samir Sayadi (samir.sayadi@juntadeandalucia.es)

Support from the above partners is optional and subject to their strategic planning and budgets.

Key Provisions

The above are statements of cooperation between the Parties, indicating their intentions to collaborate and develop relationships to further mutual objectives. The MoC is not intended to be a legally binding document.

The parties agree to work together based on the following principles:

- **Mutual benefit:** Ensuring that all parties derive value from the collaboration.
- **Transparency:** Open communication and full disclosure of information related to ongoing projects, funding opportunities, and decision-making processes.
- **Inclusivity:** Encourage participation from a broad range of stakeholders.
- **Sustainability:** Prioritizing long-term outcomes.

Any activities conducted under this MoC are subject to their inclusion in the Parties' respective strategic planning and budgets (considering the availability of funds). They shall be carried out following their respective rules and practices.

Any specific joint activities decided at a later point in time will be reflected in separate oral or written agreements. Unless expressly agreed otherwise in the specific separate agreements, the general provisions of the present MoC will apply.

Any joint activities or other forms of collaboration may include several Parties, but not necessarily all of them. In other words, a subset of the Parties (e.g. two regional authorities) may decide to collaborate without being required to inform or invite the remaining Parties.

Additional funding may be sought through European Union programmes and public-private partnerships.

4. Confidentiality and Disclosure of Information

The Parties reserve the right to disclose to the public this MoC and information concerning activities carried out under this MoC following their relevant policies.

The Parties undertake to keep confidential any information, documents or other material communicated to them as confidential or the disclosure of which may be prejudicial to any Party until or unless the content becomes publicly available.

5. Entry into Operation and Duration

The present MoC will enter into operation on the day of its signature by all Parties. It will be applicable for three (3) years. Also, it may be renewed for further periods upon the written agreement of all Parties. Furthermore, the present MoC can be amended at any time by mutual agreement and shall become effective once all Parties have consented to the modification in writing.

The present MoC may be terminated at any time by the consent of all Parties. Also, any Party can leave the MoC under the condition that it provides three (3) months' written notice before the intended

leave date to the other Parties. In any case, the Parties should agree on steps to ensure that the activities initiated under the MoC are brought to a prompt and orderly conclusion.

In case of any dispute or difference between the Parties arising from the validity, interpretation or implementation of the terms of the present MoC, the Parties shall settle it amicably by mutual agreement.

6. Signature

I hereby consent to become a Party in the Memorandum of Collaboration identified above. I accept all the rights and obligations of a Party starting from May 13th 2025.

For the Region of Andalusia:

Name: Mar Cátedra Cerón

Position: Technical Advisor of the General Secretariat for Agriculture, Livestock and Food. Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development of the Regional Government of Andalusia

Email: mariam.catedra@juntadeandalucia.es

Date: May 13th 2025

Signature:

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Mar Cátedra Cerón', written over a large, light blue circular scribble.

For the Region of Baden-Württemberg :

Name: Dr. Petra Püchner

Position: Commissioner for Europe of the Minister of Economic Affairs, Labour and Tourism Baden-Württemberg

Email: Petra.Puechner@steinbeis-europa.de

Date: May 13th 2025

Signature:

i.A.

For the Region of Central Macedonia:

Name: Dimitrios Vlachos

Position: Head of Department of Industry, Energy and Natural Resources

Email: d.vlachos@pkm.gov.gr

Date: May 13th 2025

Signature:

For the Southern Region of Ireland:

Name: Colm Walsh

Position: EU Projects Officer, Southern Regional Assembly

Email: cwalsh@southernassembly.ie

Date: May 13th 2025

Signature:

For the Region of Zilina:

Name: Katarína Janurová

Position: Director of the Development Agency of the Žilina Self-Governing Region

Email: kjanurova@razsk.sk

Date: May 13th 2025

Signature:

A handwritten signature in blue ink, consisting of several fluid, connected strokes that form a stylized representation of the name Katarína Janurová.

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	www.razsk.sk
MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	www.circbio.ie
ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	www.auth.gr
REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	www.pkm.gov.gr
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	www.southernassembly.ie

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